
An overview of Women Empowerment of Tea Industry in India

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Abstract Women Empowerment is the process by which women are allowed to take a part with men to build a society. It consists to increase the power of women by providing education, training, Jobs etc. Few decades ago, Women were not allowed to go to school in India but now, Women are taking equal competition with men in different sectors of the country.

In this study, we are trying to analyse how tea industry full fill their task towards their holistic development of their workers (especially women workers)... Primary information are collected from the survey. Secondary Information are collected from newspaper, Journal & Public domain. .

It is well documented that tea industry is an eco-friendly industry. More than 50% workers are women. Tea industry has already taken various steps to up-lift the workers specially women workers.

Keywords Women Empowerment, 50% workers are women, Tea Industry.

Introduction

Women Empowerment is the process by which women are allowed to take a part with men to build a society. It consists to increase the power of women by providing education, training, Jobs etc. Few decades ago, Women were not allowed to go to school in India but now, Women are taking equal competition with men in different sectors of the country.

Brief Scenario of women empowerment in India:

In the year 1848, AD first women educator was found. After 100 years, India got women Prime Minister Indira Gandhi who was the first female Prime Minister but after that, women achieved many landmarks. Such as the first Indian women who travel in the space Kalpana Chaola.

In 1985 UN 'third world conference was organised in Kenia. The topic of the conference was redistribution of social and economic rights for the women. The United Nation Development Fund for Women (UNDFW) has emphasized the below- mention issues for the women empowerment.

- To gather the knowledge of gender in-equality and the process by which this in- equality can be resolved in the society.
- To developed self-confident and believes and helps to get control once life.

At present, women empowerment is a vital issue and central government has already emphasized on that issue. The Indian Constitution permits the right of gender equality. From the fifth five-year plan (1974-78), Indian Government focused on women towards their holistic development. Now it is a national 4th issue to develop the status for the women. The 73 & 74th Amendments (1993) of the constitution states that the women have seat for reservation in Paunch yet & Municipality.

It is well documented that tea industry is an eco-friendly industry. More than 50% workers are women. Tea industry has already taken various steps to up-lift the workers specially women workers.

Objective of the Study

- In this study we are trying to analyse the brief scenario of tea industry in the North Eastern Region.
- In this paper we are also trying to identify how tea industry full fill their task towards their holistic development of their tea Plantations women workers.

Table 1: Statewise tea plantation and the area (Source: Tea Board of India)

State	Organised sector		Enumerated STG as on 31.03.2022		Total	
	No of Tea Gardens	Tea Area (Ha)	No. of STGS	Tea Area (Ha)	Growers	Tea área (Ha)
Assam	762	23261.73	422415	114848	123177	347809.73
West Bengal	449	114479.37	36559	24212	37008	138691.37
Other North India	116	12115.93	16148	19500	16264	31615.93
North India	1327	359557.03	175122	158560	176449	518117.03
Tamil Nadu	129	29503.85	46481	34409	46610	63912.85
Kerala	95	3036.82	7923	5344	8018	35650.82
Karnataka	16	2093			16	2093
South India	240	61903.67	54404	39753	54644	101656.67
All India	1567	421460.70	229526	198313	231093	619773.60

Table 2: Total tea production all over India during 2021-2022(category wise) Qty.in M.Kg (Source: Tea Board)

Month	CTC	Orthodox	Green	Total
Jan 21	12.87	2.54	0.48	15.89
Feb 21	14.63	2.42	0.45	17.50
March 21	59.45	5.92	1.08	66.45
April 21	64.86	8.79	1.05	74.70
May 21	92.14	8.56	1.85	102.55
June 21	154.25	14.42	2.37	171.04
July 21	161.17	16.51	2.77	180.45
Aug 21	153.51	15.31	2.80	171.62
Sept 21	146.06	14.56	2.55	163.17
Oct 21	176.27	14.27	2.45	192.99
Nov 21	112.40	7.14	1.31	126.85
Dec 21	61.66	3.46	0.79	65.85
2021	1209.27	113.84	19.95	1343.06
Jan 22	13.23	2.63	0.36	16.22
Feb 22	13.21	2.76	0.57	16.48
March 22	62.87	4.78	0.53	68.48
2021-2022	1211.63	113.07	19.70	1344.40

Figure 2: Total tea production all over India during 2021-2022(category wise) Qty.in M.Kg

Literature Review

Singh, N.K. (2001) observed that in the past how tea industry fulfils their task towards their holistic development of their workers. He focussed on the social, political awareness and the various activities of women workers in the tea plantation area at the North-Eastern Region. He concluded that though various steps had taken by the tea industry but not very much development being observe red of the women tea plantation workers. Women workers are dominated by the male workers in the tea plantation area.

Mridusmita Duara and Sambit Mallick (2012) discussed that in India, Assam is highest tea producing state. But there are two major problems:

- Migration of workers
- Exploitation of Women Workers

The authors also highlighted that how labour conditions are declining and they also focussed the exploitation of women workers in the various district of Assam.

Paranami Laskar (2020) discussed about the problem of women workers in the tea plantation area. Upliftmen of the women workers are not really being observed. They are exploited by the following ways:

- Socially
- Mentally
- Physically
- Economically

The author has made an attempt to focus the women empowerment in the tea plantation area in Assam. Author has used primary and secondary data to make an attempt. The Author concluded that women empowerment is much more necessary in the tea plantation area in Assam.

Research Methodology

Sample Size

In my paper I have chosen well organised Tea plantation which is JitiTea Plantation under Goodricke Group Limited in West Bengal. This Company is the gamut player in the Indian tea industry. I had talked to the manager of the estate and he had given the clear idea about their holistic development of their women tea plantation workers.

Data Source

Primary information has been collected through personal interviews from the management. Secondary information is collected from the newspaper, Journal & Public domain.

Survey Period

Information's have been collected from recent published data & public domain as well as personal interview during end of October, 2018.

Finding and Discussion

Goodricke Group Limited

Goodricke Group Limited is an India-based company. Whose register office in West Bengal. It is Private sector tea producing Company. The Company was established on 14th June 1977. The Company's main objective is to spread tea globally as well as to create more employment in the plantation area specially women workers.

Table 3: The Existing Tea estates of Goodricke Group Limited (Source: <https://www.goodricke.com/gardens>)

States/District	No. of Tea Estates
Darjeeling	05
Assam	12
Dooars	11
Total	28

Figure 3: The Existing Tea estates of Goodricke Group Limited

Women Empowerment Activities of Jiti tea estate (Goodricke Group Limited)

I have visited Jiti Tea Estate in October 2018 which is under Jalpaiguri District. & the owner of the tea Estate is Goodricke Group Limited. I had talked to the senior manager of the tea Estate. He said the company has already done the following activities for their female tea plantation workers.

- **Providing LPG Gases-** As per Plantation Labour Act, LPG gases are provided by the Tea Estate instead of fire hood.
- **Financial Advice-** The management also provides training programme to the female workers how to save money.
- **Scholarships** - Those students who use to get 60-75% are eligible to receive this Mr. Peter Legett Scholarship.
- **Training from human Trafficking-** The Tea Estate provides training programme for human trafficking for the workers especially young Girl.
- **Providing Education to the worker** – The management provides education to the worker (especially female worker) how to operate machine.
- **Goodricke School for Special Child-** The Company set up a school for special child. The school is situated in Siliguri. When I visited there the school was celebrating 25th year. The building was set up on 2003.

The School has some special activities for special children.

- Training and Empowerment
- Faculty training
- Parents' training
- Vocational Re-habitation-Tea packaging
- Activities of daily living
- Structure play
- Hydrotherapy
- Tea packaging unit

Conclusions and Recommendations

- Tea Industry has already played a gamut role for women empowerment.
- More than 50% workers are women in the tea industry.
- Being Jiti estate is situated in the remote corner of the country the estate has already taken various measures to up-lift their workers (Specially Women workers) & local people.

- Tea industry should focus more on the women empowerment in the tea plantation area at North East Region.

References

- [1]. Business Wire (2017, June12). Assessment of the Indian Tea Industry 2017 - Research and Markets. Retrieved from <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20170612005520/en/Assessment-Indian-Tea-Industry-2017---Research>
- [2]. Christian R. Bueno Montaldo. (2013, May). Literature Review: Sustainable Development Approaches for Rural Development and Poverty Alleviation & Community Capacity Building for Rural Development and Poverty Alleviation Retrieved from <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/877LR%20Sustainable%20Development%20v2.pdf>
- [3]. Goodricke Group Limited. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goodricke_Group_Limited#Gardens
- [4]. Goodricke The Tea People. (n.d). Retrieved from <http://www.goodricke.com/about>
- [5]. Robert Beaghole. (2015, July 15). Sustainable human development—but how? Retrieved from [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(15\)61215-6/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(15)61215-6/fulltext)
- [6]. Sandip kumar Santra. (2014, December). Implementation of Sustainability as a Strategy in Tea Industry for Saving on Social Cost and Maintaining Economic Viability: Case Study of a Tea Garden in the District of Darjeeling, West Bengal. Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Global Business, Economics, Finance and Social Sciences (GB14Mumbai Conference) Mumbai, India. 19-21 December 2014 ISBN: 978-1-941505-21-2 Paper ID: M429, Page no: 1-26.
- [7]. Scottish Government Riaghaltasna h-alba gov.scot (2006). Sustainable Development: A Review of International Literature. Theories and principles for sustainable development Retrieved from <https://www2.gov.scot/Publications/2006/05/23091323/4>
- [8]. Sustainable development. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainable_development.
- [9]. Pradyut Guha and Tiken Das, (n.d). Inequality and Incidence of Poverty among Labourer in Tea Plantation Sector; A case study of Dibrugarh District of Assam.
- [10]. R.K Mishra, Shulgana Sarkar and Punam Singh, (n.d) Corporate Social Responsibility: The Role of Corporate for a Sustainable Tomorrow.
- [11]. Sustainable Human Development, (n.d). retrieve from <https://www.google.com/search?client=firefox-d&q=sustainable+human+developments>
- [12]. Sustainable Development (n.d.) retrieve from https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainable_development.
- [13]. Indian Tea Industry (n.d) Retrieved from <https://www.indianmirror.com/indian-industries/tea.html>.
- [14]. Tea workers in West Bengal on strike, demand higher minimum wage (2018, August 08), Retrieved From <https://www.groundxero.in/2018/08/08/tea-workers-in-west-bengal-on-strike-demand-higher-minimum-wage/>
- [15]. Women Empowerment Initiatives (n.d.). retrieve from <http://vikaspedia.in/social-welfare/women-and-child-development/women-development-1/women-empowerment-in-india>
- [16]. Goodricke Group Limited (n.d.) retrieve from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goodricke_Group_Limited
- [17]. Singh, N.K. (2001) Article Name “Role of women workers in the tea industry of North East Region” publisher name “Classical Publishing” ISBN No.8170543207 retrieve from <https://www.cabdirect.org/cabdirect/abstract/20026791886>
- [18]. Laskar Pranami (2020) Article Name “Women Empowerment in the Tea Garden Areas of Assam: A Case Study on Kondoli Tea Estate of Nagaon District” VoL63 No.6 (2020)
- [19]. Duara Mridusmita and Sambit Mallick (2012) Article Name “Tea Industry in Assam (India): Issues of Migration and Gender Discrimination” DOI: 10.7763/IPEDR. 2012. V54. Page-35

